

Efficient Implementation of Serial and Parallel Support Vector Machine Training with a Multi-Parameter Kernel for Large-Scale Data Mining

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Abstract— This work deals with aspects of support vector learning for large-scale data mining tasks. Based on a decomposition algorithm that can be run in serial and parallel mode we introduce a data transformation that allows for the usage of an expensive generalized kernel without additional costs. In order to speed up the decomposition algorithm we analyze the problem of working set selection for large data sets and analyze the influence of the working set sizes onto the scalability of the parallel decomposition scheme. Our modifications and settings lead to improvement of support vector learning performance and thus allow using extensive parameter search methods to optimize classification accuracy.

Keywords— Support Vector Machines, Shared Memory Parallel Computing, Large Data

I. INTRODUCTION

DURING the last years data mining tasks have shifted from small data sets to large-scale problems with a lot of noise in the data. At the same time industry requires complex models with well tuned parameters and promising results for test data.

Support vector machines (SVMs) for classification and regression are powerful methods of machine learning. They have been widely studied and applied to hard, but mostly small classification problems. These so-called kernel methods have good generalization properties, which means that the classification function works well on data that have not been used during the training. However, SVM training methods suffer from large and noisy data. Important SVM research issues include

- applicability [1],
- generalization abilities [2],
- convergence properties [3],
- parameter selection methods [4],
- interpretational aspects [5],

and many more.

In addition to these fundamental issues, the ability to handle problems of ever increasing size is of vital interest because in many applications the amount of data grows exponentially [6]. For these problems, SVM training time becomes a major

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concern, particularly when applying parameter selection methods that force the user to perform dozens or hundreds of SVM trainings. Due to extreme training times complex SVM models and intelligent parameter tuning have been employed only rarely, so that users often ended up with suboptimal classifiers and started to use other parameter free data mining methods with worse generalization properties.

For these reasons, research on efficient and fast SVM classification methods has been intensified during the last years, leading to approaches for

- fast serial training [7],
- efficient parameter selection methods [8],
- fast multi-class learning [9],
- parallel parameter tuning [10],
- parallel validation methods [11], and
- parallel training methods [12].

Issues of parallel support vector machines are comparatively new. They emerged during the last few years. Really parallel implementations are rare since most of the parallel algorithms realize simple farming jobs like parallel cross validation tasks. Farming reduces overall running time but is not able to improve the performance of SVM training itself in general.

In our work we now try to combine aspects of efficient SVM training techniques with parallelization. Based on a decomposition algorithm that can be run in serial and parallel mode we discuss modifications of the program flow that lead to significantly faster SVM training for large data sets, both in serial and parallel mode.

The paper is organized as follows. In Sect. II we review basics of binary SVM classification. In Sect. III we describe our serial and parallel SVM algorithm. Our computing system as well as the data set used for our experiments are introduced in Sect. IV. In Sect. V we discuss the influence of kernel computations onto training time and introduce our approach of data transformation for efficient usage of the powerful multi-parameter Gaussian kernel. The issue of optimal working set selection for SVM training is discussed in Sect. VI.

II. SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINES

Support vector learning [13] is a well known and reliable data mining method. We consider the problem of supervised binary classification which means to use a training data set

$$\{(\mathbf{x}_i, y_i) \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \{-1, 1\}, i = 1, \dots, l\}$$

to learn a binary decision function

$$h(\mathbf{x}) = \text{sgn}(f(\mathbf{x})),$$

where we define the signum function in a modified form as

$$\text{sgn}(a) = \begin{cases} +1, & a \geq 0 \\ -1, & a < 0 \end{cases} \quad (a \in \mathbb{R}).$$

The real-valued nonlinear classification function f is defined as [14]

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^l y_i \alpha_i K(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}) + b. \quad (1)$$

The kernel function K [15], which can be interpreted as a local measure of similarity between training points, is used to avoid a so-called feature mapping of the data and to construct a nonlinear classifier based on a simple linear learning approach. In this work we analyze the so-called Gaussian kernel, which is very popular. A definition of this kernel will be given in Sect. V.

The problem specific classification parameters $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^l$ and $b \in \mathbb{R}$ of (1) are given implicitly through the training data and some SVM specific learning parameters [16]. These learning parameters, e.g. the kernel type and its parameter(s), have to be set before training and can be adjusted via parameter optimization [10].

It is well known [14] that the optimal vector α^* can be computed via the solution of the dual quadratic program (QP)

$$\min_{\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^l} g(\alpha) := \frac{1}{2} \alpha^T H \alpha - \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i \quad (2)$$

with

$$H \in \mathbb{R}^{l \times l}, \quad H_{ij} = y_i K(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) y_j \quad (1 \leq i, j \leq l),$$

constrained to

$$\alpha^T \mathbf{y} = 0, \quad 0 \leq \alpha_i \leq C \quad (i = 1, \dots, l).$$

The parameter $C > 0$ is important for a natural weighting between the competing goals of training error minimization and generalization. For details we refer to the work [14] and the tutorial [17].

The computation of the threshold b^* is based on the so-called Karush–Kuhn–Tucker conditions [14] for the primal form of the problem (2). Given the unique and global dual solution α^* (the vector of Lagrange multipliers) it is easy to show that

$$0 = \alpha_i^* \cdot [y_i \cdot f(\mathbf{x}_i) + \xi_i^* - 1], \quad 0 = \xi_i^* \cdot (\alpha_i^* - C)$$

hold for all $i = 1, \dots, l$. The slack vector $\xi \in \mathbb{R}_+^l$, originally defined in the primal problem, results from the soft margin approach of SVM learning [14] which is used in most of the available software packages to allow for training errors [18]–[20]. Since we solve the dual problem, the slack values are unknown. Therefore we have to use the so called nonbound support vectors to compute b^* . A nonbound support vector \mathbf{x}_i is characterized by $\alpha_i^* \in (0, C)$. See [14] for detailed

information on slack variables, support vectors and bounds. Using (1) we derive

$$0 = \alpha_i^* \left[y_i \left(\sum_{j=1}^l \alpha_j^* y_j K(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) + b^* \right) + \xi_i - 1 \right].$$

for all training points and thus

$$b^* = y_i - \sum_{j=1}^l \alpha_j^* y_j K(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j)$$

for all nonbound support vectors \mathbf{x}_i .

Note that (2) is a quadratic optimization problem with a dense matrix H . For large data the solution of this problem—the so called training stage—is very expensive. In the following section we shortly describe our efficient SVM training method.

III. EFFICIENT SERIAL AND PARALLEL SVM TRAINING

This work is based on the SVM training method described in [21]. We briefly review the most important features of the serial and parallel implementations.

We are working with the well known decomposition scheme [22] for the solution of (2). This scheme is summarized in Fig. 1. It repeatedly performs the following four steps.

- 1) Select \hat{l} “active” variables from the l free variables α_i , the so-called working set. In our implementation the working set is made up from points violating the Karush–Kuhn–Tucker conditions; see [16] for more details.
- 2) Restrict the optimization in (2) to the active variables and fix the remaining ones. Prepare the submatrix $H_{\text{active}} \in \mathbb{R}^{\hat{l} \times \hat{l}}$ for the restricted problem and the submatrix $H_{\text{mixed}} \in \mathbb{R}^{(l-\hat{l}) \times \hat{l}}$ for the stopping criterion.
- 3) Check for convergence. The solution of (2) is found if step 1 yields an empty working set.
- 4) Solve the restricted problem.

Fig. 1. Decomposition scheme for SVM training.

The idea of splitting the quadratic problem into active and inactive parts iteratively is not new [23]. One feature that makes this approach particularly attractive for SVM training is the flexibility concerning the size \hat{l} . Large values of \hat{l} place high demands on memory because \hat{l} columns of H (i.e., $\hat{l} \cdot l$

entries) must be stored. In the extreme case $\hat{l} = l$, the whole matrix H is required. On the other hand, choosing $\hat{l} < l$ may lead to kernel values being re-computed several times when a variable α_i switches between the “inactive” and “active” states. Therefore most SVM software packages avoid recomputation of the columns of H . They implement caching of kernel values to speed up training time. For example, [20] uses the well-known least-recently-used cache strategy. Unfortunately, the caching strategies are difficult and system dependent.

For complex learning models on large data a huge amount of time is consumed by the kernel function evaluations in the decomposition step, where the kernel matrices are updated in every iteration. It is known [21] that training time is a function of the working set size \hat{l} that acts as a mediator between the alternating work in the outer decomposition loop and the inner solver. Large working sets slow down the solution of each quadratic subproblem, whereas small working sets lead to a large number of decomposition iterations until convergence is reached, which means that a lot of kernel function evaluations take place.

The SVM training time also depends on the efficiency of the algorithm that solves the subproblems. We use the generalized variable projection method introduced in [24] as an inner solver.

Usually small working sets have been used to avoid expensive subproblems [25]. However, our powerful computing systems now allow for very large working sets. Thus we have to determine the optimal value for \hat{l} that minimizes the sum of times for inner solver computations and decomposition workload.

One way to improve the performance of SVM training is parallelization. Our parallel SVM training method does not implement a simple farming approach, but a real parallel flow. It is based on the observation [21] that typically more than 90% of the overall time is spent in the kernel evaluations and in the matrix–vector and vector–vector operations of the inner solver; for very large data sets this fraction is even higher. We decided to address these computational bottlenecks with a shared memory parallelization, using OpenMP work sharing for the kernel computations and relying on the parallelized numerical linear algebra kernels available in the *ESSLSMP* library for the compute-intensive parts of the inner solver. Fig. 2 shows the parallel parts (shaded) of the decomposition scheme.

However, in order to achieve optimum performance, the parallelization should be complemented with techniques that reduce the learning time also in the serial case. In Sect. V and VI we will discuss our approaches for faster SVM training and their results.

IV. CHARACTERISTICS OF DATA AND COMPUTING SYSTEM

For all tests reported here we used the so-called adult data set from [26], which is the data set with the largest number of training instances in the database. The task for this set is to predict whether someone’s income exceeds a certain threshold. Thus we have a binary classification problem. The number

Fig. 2. Extension of the serial algorithm for parallel SVM training.

of training points is 32561. Out of the 14 attributes, 6 are continuous, and 8 are discrete. There are plenty of missing values for the discrete attributes. These were replaced with either the value that occurred most frequently for the particular attribute or with a new value, if the number of missing values for the attribute was very high.

The adult data set was also used in [27], but only for 16000 training points. There, a new parallel MPI based SVM learning method for distributed memory systems has been described. We used nearly all points for the training, i.e., 30000.

Our serial and parallel experiments were made on the Juelich Multi Processor (JUMP) at Research Centre Juelich [28]. JUMP is a distributed shared memory parallel computer consisting of 41 frames (nodes). Each node contains 32 IBM Power4+ processors running at 1.7 GHz, and 128 GB shared main memory. All in all the 1312 processors have an aggregate peak performance of 8.9 TFlop/s. We have tested on a single node of JUMP. Test results are given in the following two sections.

V. EFFICIENT KERNEL EVALUATIONS

As we discussed in Sect. I the training of support vector machines on large data is a challenging problem [25], [29]. A vast amount of time is always consumed by the expensive kernel function evaluations [21], no matter which kernel type is used.

In this section we present our new approach of efficient kernel evaluations that includes the usage of a multi-parameter kernel.

The usual Gaussian kernel [30]

$$K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}) = \exp\left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z}\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad (3)$$

which is used in many data analysis tools, includes a single division operation for each kernel function evaluation. $\sigma > 0$ is the constant width of the kernel. This parameter is central for SVM learning with the Gaussian kernel. It has to be chosen carefully to avoid overfitting effects.

The division operation in (3) can be replaced with a less expensive multiplication by setting

$$\tilde{\sigma} = \frac{1}{2 \cdot \sigma^2}$$

once already before SVM training and evaluating the kernel as

$$K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}) = \exp(-\tilde{\sigma}\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z}\|^2). \quad (4)$$

This simple modification is not possible for the generalized, multi-parameter Gaussian kernel [16]

$$K_M(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}) = \exp\left(-\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(x_k - z_k)^2}{2\sigma_k^2}\right). \quad (5)$$

This kernel assigns a different width $\sigma_k \geq 0$ for each feature k ($k = 1, \dots, n$). For unbalanced data sets this kernel can lead to significantly better SVMs than the standard kernel; cf. [10]. Unfortunately the n divisions make this kernel rather expensive and thus responsible for long SVM training times. Therefore it is used only rarely [10].

It is possible to avoid all parameter-dependent operations inside the kernel function. To this end we first rewrite the kernel (3) as

$$K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}) = \exp\left(-\sum_{k=1}^n \left(\frac{x_k - z_k}{\sqrt{2}\sigma}\right)^2\right).$$

Thus, an initial scaling of the training points according to

$$t(\mathbf{x}) := \frac{\mathbf{x}}{\sqrt{2}\sigma} \quad (6)$$

allows the standard kernel to be evaluated as

$$K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}) = \exp(-\|t(\mathbf{x}) - t(\mathbf{z})\|^2). \quad (7)$$

Similarly, the scaling

$$\tilde{t}(\mathbf{x}) := \left(\frac{x_1}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_1}, \dots, \frac{x_n}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_n}\right), \quad (8)$$

leads to

$$K_M(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}) = \exp(-\|\tilde{t}(\mathbf{x}) - \tilde{t}(\mathbf{z})\|^2). \quad (9)$$

Note that in this formulation the generalized and the standard kernel differ only in the initial transformation of the data. The transformation step has to be done before SVM training and is independent of \hat{l} and other settings of the decomposition method.

We will now assess the savings induced by our approach, first with respect to the number of divisions and then to overall learning time.

For a training set with l instances and n attributes the number of divisions in the initial transformation is simply given by the number of entries in the original data matrix, that is,

$$d_T = l \cdot n.$$

For our implementation of the decomposition algorithm the number of divisions in the standard kernel function evaluations is given by

$$d_E = D \cdot l \cdot \hat{l},$$

where D is the number of decomposition steps and \hat{l} is the working set size. For the generalized kernel, d_E is higher by a factor of n .

Since our approach replaces the divisions of the kernel evaluations with those of the data transformation, the overall number of divisions is reduced by a factor of d_E/d_T . In Table I we show these ratios for the adult data set. We computed the number d_E for the (standard) kernel evaluations and different working set sizes. Note that for all tests we have

$$d_T = 30000 \cdot 14 = 420000.$$

TABLE I

RATIO OF THE NUMBERS OF DIVISIONS IN THE APPROACHES (3) AND (7).

\hat{l}	D	d_E	d_E/d_T
5000	37	$5550 \cdot 10^6$	13200
10000	16	$4800 \cdot 10^6$	11400
15000	10	$4500 \cdot 10^6$	10700
20000	5	$3000 \cdot 10^6$	7100
25000	2	$1500 \cdot 10^6$	3600
30000	1	$900 \cdot 10^6$	2100

The data indicate that the savings are highest for small values of \hat{l} . However, a large factor does not automatically minimize the overall time. We will analyze overall running time for different working set sizes in the next section.

Now we consider the execution time for different ways of kernel computations. We measure the time that is spent to transform the data as well as the time used to solve the quadratic optimization problem, i.e., the ensuing training, which includes the kernel computations. We consider the following five variants for kernel evaluation:

- K_1 : standard kernel (3) with one division,
- K_2 : standard kernel (4) with one multiplication,
- K_3 : multi-parameter kernel (5) with n divisions,
- K_4 : standard kernel (7) with pre-scaling, and
- K_5 : multi-parameter kernel (9) with pre-scaling.

In Table II we show the training time (in seconds) of our support vector machine for these kernels. We performed the tests for a working set size of 10000 to show the amount of time that can be saved. Since the number of kernel evaluations depends on the working set size, too, the effects can vary. We will analyze the influence of the working set size onto the overall training time in the next section.

TABLE II

INFLUENCE OF THE KERNEL EVALUATION METHOD ONTO THE OVERALL TRAINING TIME.

	pre-scaling	training
K_1	-	1529.2
K_2	-	1452.7
K_3	-	2412.3
K_4	0.01	1122.3
K_5	0.02	1122.3

From Table II we conclude the following:

- Replacing the division with a multiplication gives only a minor improvement on our machine [28].
- For our example the initial data transformation reduces the overall training time by 30% for the standard kernel and by more than 50% for the generalized kernel.

- The preceding discussion suggests that the training time results for K_4 and K_5 should be equal, which indeed is true. This means that the multi-parameter kernel essentially comes for free—except for the fact that it involves more learning parameters, which must be set before the training.
- The time for the initial transformation is negligible. It might be reduced even further with an easy-to-implement parallel version.

VI. OPTIMAL WORKING SET SIZE

In this section we analyze the influence of the working set size \hat{l} on the number of decomposition steps, D , the number of kernel evaluations, E , and the training time. In [21] we observed that for a data set with 10000 points and working set sizes between 1000 and 7000 points there were nearly no differences between the training times. The situation is different for the much larger adult data set with its 30000 points.

In Table III we summarize the test results we achieved for serial SVM training. All tests were performed with the kernel (9), which is the most efficient one. The training times do not include the transformation times, which are negligible and do not depend on \hat{l} . Computation times are given in seconds as before. In addition to medium-sized working sets we also consider very small and extremely large working sets.

TABLE III
 NUMBER OF DECOMPOSITION STEPS AND OF KERNEL EVALUATIONS, AND TRAINING TIMES FOR DIFFERENT WORKING SET SIZES.

\hat{l}	D	E	time
50	5831	$8.747 \cdot 10^9$	1869.3
100	2828	$8.484 \cdot 10^9$	1779.6
500	497	$7.455 \cdot 10^9$	1618.1
1000	238	$7.140 \cdot 10^9$	1508.2
2000	113	$6.780 \cdot 10^9$	1449.6
5000	37	$5.550 \cdot 10^9$	1212.1
10000	16	$4.800 \cdot 10^9$	1108.0
15000	10	$4.500 \cdot 10^9$	1099.1
20000	5	$3.000 \cdot 10^9$	780.2
25000	2	$1.500 \cdot 10^9$	430.4
30000	1	$0.900 \cdot 10^9$	267.8

Comparing the graphs for E and the time in Fig. 3 confirms the dominating effect of the kernel evaluations on the training time. From the serial experiments we conclude that the largest possible working set minimizes the training time.

Now we consider the problem of working set selection for parallel SVM training. For the parallel mode we try to find out whether for a fixed number of threads the same number \hat{l} also leads to the minimal consumption of time or not. Since our decomposition algorithm consists of two parallelized parts that show different behavior for varying working set sizes we cannot predict the effects for the parallel algorithm easily. However, some aspects are already known. The efficiency of the parallel numerical linear algebra kernels (*ESSLSMP* routines on the JUMP) is low for small working set sizes since the problem sizes within the QP solver solely correspond to the working set size and not to the overall problem size l . The

Fig. 3. Number of kernel evaluations and training time for different values of \hat{l} .

definition of “small” is somewhat vague and depends on the computing system to be used as well as the number of threads, but of course a value $\hat{l} = 1000$ is not sufficient for satisfactory speedups of *ESSLSMP* routines.

In Table IV we show results of parallel SVM training for two large working set sizes and different numbers of threads. For $\hat{l} = 15000$ the speedups tend to be slightly larger than for the extreme case $\hat{l} = l$. This is due to the fact that for $\hat{l} = 30000$ the influence of sequential parts of the code is higher. For example, since the number of decomposition steps—and therefore of kernel matrix updates—is only one, the relative contribution of this perfectly scalable routine is smaller.

TABLE IV
 SPEEDUP VALUES FOR TWO DIFFERENT WORKING SET SIZES.

	$\hat{l} = 15000$		$\hat{l} = 30000$	
	time	speedup	time	speedup
serial	1108.0	–	267.8	–
2 threads	535.6	2.1	144.6	1.9
3 threads	345.1	3.2	106.9	2.5
4 threads	263.4	4.2	78.6	3.4
5 threads	223.2	5.0	66.8	4.0
6 threads	231.9	4.8	56.8	4.7
7 threads	220.7	5.0	48.8	5.5
8 threads	229.7	4.8	49.9	5.4

Our shared memory parallelization yields satisfactory speedups for small numbers of processors, but it does not scale to high numbers of processors. Indeed, the speedups did not exceed 5 and 5.5, and these were obtained with 5 and 7 processors. Note that the SVM training involves at most level-2 numerical linear algebra kernels, which can make only very limited use of the processors’ caches. Therefore the number of data accesses increases with the number of threads, until the maximum bandwidth of the memory is reached.

The restriction of our shared memory parallelization to small numbers of processors is, however, not a severe limitation. If large numbers of processors are available, then two additional levels of parallelism may be exploited with the message passing paradigm: The k -fold cross validation, which requires training of k SVMs on different data, is easily parallelized with a farming approach, and a parallel optimizer can be used to determine adequate settings for the learning parameters, such as C and the σ_i .

The setting $\hat{l} = 30000$ and 7 threads led to the minimal training time. Since the data transformation needed 0.02 seconds, the overall time for the generalized kernel is also 48.8 seconds. Comparing this value with the 2412.3 seconds given in Table II we observe that combining the pre-scaling, an optimal working set size, and a moderate degree of parallelism may result in an overall speedup of almost 50.

Based on the results in Sect. V and the Tables III and IV we propose the following settings for efficient training of support vector machines:

- a priori transformation of the training data according to (6) or (8),
- implementation of the modified kernel (7) and (9) respectively,
- choice of working sets as large as the available memory allows, and
- usage of an appropriate number of threads for parallel training; 6 may be a reasonable upper bound, cf. Table IV.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We proposed techniques for the efficient serial and parallel training of support vector machines for large data sets. We introduced a data transformation that reduced training time for the adult data set. In combination with the choice of a reasonable working set size the improvement of support vector learning performance can be substantial.

In the future we plan to combine our parallel support vector learning algorithm with efficient parameter optimization methods [10]. This combination would lead to a fully automated approach for fast and reliable support vector learning for the classification of large data sets.

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